

FACTORS OF IMPROVING RUSSIAN LANGUAGE TEACHERS' PROFESSIONAL SKILLS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10436394>

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Abstract: *Teacher professional competence is considered to be in the center of the educational system. In this article attention is given to developing pupils' competence through teachers' professional tactics as a main factor in secondary schools*

The issue of professional skill has always been one of the key issues in the public education system. This article examines the factors affecting the improvement of the professional skills of a teacher of a modern secondary school

Keywords: *competence, professional competence, way, abilities, opportunity, development, teacher development*

Being tactful is a moral rule for every person, in particular for a teacher. After all, the choice of life path and the upbringing of the individual depend on the teacher. At the same time, pedagogical tact should be considered as a professional quality of a teacher, a component of his skill. It represents a set of not only personal qualities (respect for the student's personality, love for children, correctness, politeness), but also the formation of skills in choosing the right approach to students, that is, it is a means of influence involved in the adjustment and upbringing of children.

When working, the teacher must speak with the greatest caution. Try to apply various methods in the most optimal, unobtrusive, delicate way. At the same time, the teacher should monitor his behavior. After all, any deviation in the teacher's actions can provoke a backlash among students: if the teacher is overly demanding, this will lead to disobedience, if he is overly lenient, this will lead to rudeness. The teacher's behavior should demonstrate his respect for children. Respect is formed during the lessons of getting acquainted with works of art, and the child develops a sense of self-esteem. Using the examples of images of their favorite heroes, children learn to live, love, and distinguish between positive and negative. Every teacher needs to cultivate and constantly develop self-control, self-control, and tact in communication, which are integral components of pedagogical tact and are manifested in the balance of the teacher's behavior. This is trust in the student. A teacher who pessimistically assesses the abilities and capabilities of students and emphasizes them at every opportunity clearly demonstrates not only

tactlessness. It psychologically kills the child's desire to learn. Building communication on a note of trust was, is and will be the best incentive for students to work. It is no secret that students experience great difficulties in expressing their thoughts in Russian; as a rule, the language barrier interferes, and certain complexes arise.

When testing and assessing students' knowledge, the teacher should pay special attention to his actions and behavior. An expression of the teacher's tactfulness is the ability to listen to the student's answer: to be interested, attentive to the content and form of the student's answer. It is important in this situation to show restraint if students have difficulty answering. It is important to support the student with either a smile, a glance, or a nod. But it is advisable to refrain from making comments during the response of students, especially weak ones.

It is important in this situation to show restraint if students have difficulty answering. It is important to support the student with either a smile, a glance, or a nod. But it is advisable to refrain from making comments during the response of students, especially weak ones. To do this, attention should be paid to the development of knowledge, skills and abilities of teachers. Today, every teacher as a subject of education is required to have a creative approach and dedication.

An important point in rethinking the goals and tasks facing today's teacher is the awareness of involvement in the changes taking place, an adequate assessment of one's capabilities, a reconsideration of one's attitude towards work, the rejection of stereotypes and work on oneself. Indeed, today we are faced with a task of enormous importance and long-term relevance - to educate a harmoniously developed, comprehensively prepared, competitive personality, a worthy specialist who can apply the acquired knowledge in a real situation, in practice. That is, to form and develop competencies. When developing competencies, teachers must implement student-centered learning into the pedagogical process; find new directions for the design and implementation of pedagogical tools, modern methods and technologies leading to improving the quality of the educational process. This is an important fact when forming the image of the teacher himself. The relevant question is what qualities the teacher himself should have in order to then cultivate these qualities in schoolchildren. It is important how a teacher's professional skills are demonstrated. These and other aspects posed by modern requirements for teachers are today's priority. After all, the "activity and creativity" of the teacher should turn into the activity of the students, that is, the students. The professional activity of a Russian language teacher as a carrier and transmitter of scientific information, along with the correct organization of independent work of students, should include an expansion of the functions of managing their cognitive activity. Interaction between a teacher and students based on integration is an essential dominant feature of a teacher's pedagogical activity. The ideas of the above-mentioned interaction were considered in the works of outstanding teachers: P.P. Vlonsky, L.S. Vygotsky, K.D. Ushinsky, S.T. Shatsky, A.S. Makarenko, V.A. Sukhomlinsky, A.M. Arsenyev, Y.K. Babansky, V.E. Gmurman, N.K. Goncharov, R.G.

Gurovoy, M.A. Danilova, I.A. Kairov, F.F. Korolev, V.M. Korotov, V.V. Kraevsky, I.Ya. Lerner, B.T. Likhachev T.N. Malkovskaya, M.I. Makhmutova, L.I. Novikova, G.N. Filonova, I.F. Kharlamova, N.M. .Shakhmaeva, A.A.Shibanova and others.

In theory and practice, attempts have been made repeatedly to model the personality of a professional teacher. The professionalism of a secondary school teacher has always been the focus of attention of many researchers. Many scientific works and methodological developments on this problem has been published to this day. But they have many different points of view on this issue. There is a need to conduct a targeted and comprehensive study of the features of the formation of professional skills of a Russian language teacher training in the public education system. Insufficient development and research of the problem determines its relevance. Having analyzed various approaches to determining the structure of a teacher's professional competence/competence, we came to the conclusion that most researchers, considering professional competence and competence as a structural-functional education, include in it the totality of knowledge and skills of a teacher and his professionally significant qualities, manifested in purposeful activities. A teacher's professional competencies lie in the ability to create and organize an educational and developmental environment in which it becomes possible to achieve the child's educational results, formulated as key competencies. All other more specific competencies follow from the general one and are its components.

When developing a teacher's professional competence, in our opinion, the process of becoming familiar with new methods and the taught subject is important. Agreeing with the above-mentioned aspects, we note the need for further work in this direction, we assume the implementation of such provisions as improving the technology for improving the professional skills of Russian language teachers in the continuous education system with an organic relationship between the content and the very process of forming a professional culture among students of higher educational institutions of a pedagogical direction with actual situation in the secondary school system. The list of the professional competencies of a Russian language teacher in the system of general secondary education institutions will be constantly supplemented and changed depending on the personal qualities and abilities of the teacher himself, as well as on the planned goals and objectives for a certain period of children's education.

One of the important aspects will be the implementation of work on the systemic, personal-activity, cultural orientation of the professional development of the future Russian language teacher as the main subject of the pedagogical process (or activity). This requires the development of a model of a professional teacher, the definition of indicators and evaluation indicators.

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